

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INSTAGRAM SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN INCREASING BRAND AWARENESS OF THE INTEGRATED STATISTICS SERVICE OF BPS-STATISTICS TANGERANG REGENCY

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Abstract

The low utilization of the Integrated Statistics Service (PST) of BPS-Statistics Tangerang Regency indicates a problem in the level of public brand awareness, even though the quality of service is classified as very good, so a more effective communication strategy is needed through social media marketing, especially Instagram. This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of utilizing Instagram in increasing brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency using a qualitative method through a case study approach, where data is collected through social media analytics-based observations and in-depth interviews with three internal sources, and analyzed comparatively between conditions in 2023 and 2024. The results of the study show a significant increase in the number and quality of Instagram content in 2024 compared to 2023, although the proportion of content specifically containing PST information is still relatively limited; however, the increase in audience interaction, the number of followers, and the increase in offline service users indicate that social media marketing through Instagram is effective in increasing brand awareness to reach the level of brand recognition and brand recall in the general public as well as brand dominance in the local government segment. The decline in online service users does not entirely reflect Instagram's ineffectiveness, but is influenced by external factors such as user behavior that does not follow service procedures, so strategy optimization is needed through increasing content variety and intensity, delivering more comprehensive service information, utilizing interactive features such as reels, and integrating email marketing to significantly increase engagement, loyalty, and conversion of service usage.

Keywords: *Social Media Marketing, Instagram, Brand Awareness, Integrated Statistics Service, BPS-Statistics Tangerang Regency*

INTRODUCTION

The term "Data is the New Oil" emphasizes the importance of data in today's digital age. Data has value similar to oil, which has become a primary energy source in the 20th century. Data is a crucial asset capable of driving innovation, improving decision-making, and providing a competitive advantage for companies and governments. Data utilization must be optimized to accelerate the digital transformation process and sustainable national progress (Ministry of Communication and Informatics, 2022). However, just as oil must be processed before it can be used, data also needs to be processed, analyzed, and managed properly to provide maximum benefits. BPS-Statistics Indonesia, as the official data provider, plays a crucial role in providing high-quality and reliable statistical data to various parties, including the government, academics, business actors, and the wider public. To expand its reach and improve the quality of data services, BPS initiated the Integrated Statistics Service (PST), which functions as a one-stop shop for various statistical services. PST BPS statistical services consist of two types: free and paid (free) statistical services. Free statistical services include access to macro data, statistical consultations, and statistical recommendations. Paid statistical services include purchasing micro data, purchasing electronic publications, and purchasing digital maps of statistical work areas (wilkerstat). Tariffs for paid statistical services are determined based on Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 13 of 2024 concerning Types and Tariffs for Types of Non-Tax State Revenue Applicable to the BPS-Statistics Indonesia. The PST BPS also provides a Zero Rupiah Service for all paid statistical services to certain parties, including Central Government Agencies, Regional Government Agencies, and State Institutions; Domestic Educational Institutions; and Representatives of Foreign Countries and International Institutions. Recipients of this Zero Rupiah Service can access all paid statistical services

free of charge with the requirements and maximum limits on the quantity that can be accessed as stipulated in BPS Regulation Number 2 of 2019 concerning Requirements and Procedures for Imposing a Tariff of IDR 0.00 (Zero Rupiah) on Certain Parties for Non-Tax State Revenue Applicable to the BPS-Statistics Indonesia. This Zero Rupiah Service is expected to increase the number of users of the PST BPS statistical service. Integrated Statistics Services (PST) are available at all BPS work units (satker) from the central, provincial, to district/city levels, including BPS Tangerang Regency. Various types of statistical services at the PST BPS Tangerang Regency can be accessed by visiting the PST directly at the BPS Tangerang Regency Office or online through the BPS Tangerang Regency website (tangerangkab.bps.go.id). BPS Tangerang Regency always strives to improve the quality of PST supporting facilities and infrastructure. Based on the results of the 2023 Data Needs Survey (SKD), all respondents using statistical services were satisfied with the facilities and infrastructure of BPS Tangerang Regency. The quality of service at the PST BPS Tangerang Regency is classified as very good with the Consumer Satisfaction Index (IKK) of PST BPS Tangerang Regency reaching 91.19 points and the Anti-Corruption Perception Index (IPAK) of PST BPS Tangerang Regency reaching 94.29 points. Despite improvements in the quality of PST supporting facilities and infrastructure, the level of utilization of PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services is still relatively low. Based on the 2023 BPS Tangerang Regency Performance Report (Lakin), the number of external visitors who accessed statistical services through the BPS Tangerang Regency website (online statistical service users) reached 39,787 visitors in 2023, which experienced a decrease of 2.04% in the second quarter of 2023 from 8,682 visitors in the first quarter of 2023 to 8,505 visitors in the second quarter of 2023. The 2023 BPS Tangerang Regency Performance Report (Lakin) also provides information that the number of direct visitors to the PST BPS Tangerang Regency (offline statistical service users) is very small, which only reached 12 people in 2023 or an average of only 1 person who visits directly to the PST BPS Tangerang Regency every month.

Although the IKK and IPAK PST BPS Tangerang Regency were classified as very high in 2023, these two indices were not used as components in calculating the performance of BPS work units, including BPS Tangerang Regency. The number of direct visitors to the PST BPS Tangerang Regency (offline statistics service users) and the number of external visitors accessing statistical services through the BPS Tangerang Regency website (online statistics service users) actually require attention because both are components in calculating the performance of BPS Tangerang Regency work units, especially public service performance. The still small number of users of statistical services results in less than optimal use of statistical data by the public, thus reducing the effectiveness of PST as a means of increasing statistical literacy. In addition, the still small number of users of paid statistical services also results in low revenue for BPS from paid statistical services. BPS revenue from these paid statistical services is in the form of Non-Tax State Revenue (PNBP) which is used to support the operation and development of statistical infrastructure as well as data collection and analysis activities. The low number of users of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical service indicates low brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency among the public. Therefore, efforts to increase the number of statistical service users can be carried out by first increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency among the public. According to Anand (2025), Brand Awareness is an important element in building and maintaining a successful brand presence in the market. Brand Awareness is a basic concept in marketing that refers to the extent to which consumers can recognize and remember a brand and its related attributes, including knowledge, familiarity, and consumer recognition of a particular brand and the products or services it offers (Anand, 2025).

Rahmasari and Lutfie (2020) categorize four levels of brand awareness according to David Aaker. First, Brand Recognition, where consumers are able to recognize a brand when they see it, for example by its logo, color, or packaging, even if they cannot yet recall the exact brand name. Second, Brand Recall, where consumers can recall and mention the brand name when asked or when thinking about a particular product category. Third, Top of Mind Awareness, where a brand is the first to come to mind when consumers think about a particular product category. Fourth, Brand Dominance, where the brand truly dominates the market and becomes the primary choice for consumers in the product category. At this stage, almost all consumers recognize and choose the brand without considering various alternatives. Social Media Marketing plays a crucial role in building brand awareness (Anand, 2025). Tuten and Solomon (2017) define social media marketing as a marketing practice that uses social media platforms to promote products or services, interact directly with audiences, and utilize data and analytics to improve the effectiveness of marketing campaigns. Social media itself is defined as mobile device-based technology and websites used to transform communication into interactive dialogue (Andrews & Shimp, 2013). Social media itself refers to several applications such as YouTube, WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Line that operate based on content created and shared by their users (Choedon & Lee, 2020). By sharing interesting content, providing valuable information, and actively participating in conversations, businesses can shape brand image and perception

among users (Safko & David, 2019). Positive interactions and authentic engagement on social media platforms contribute to strengthening brand reputation and customer loyalty (Anand, 2025).

Source: Publication of Public Welfare Statistics of Banten Province 2023, BPS

Figure 1. Percentage of Tangerang Regency Population Aged 5 Years and Over Using the Internet by Purpose in 2023

Based on the results of the 2023 National Socio-Economic Survey (Susenas), BPS recorded that the percentage of Tangerang Regency residents aged 5 years and above who used the internet for social media was 68.52% in 2023. Social Media is the third main purpose for Tangerang Regency residents aged 5 years and above when using the internet. In 2023, Tangerang Regency residents aged 5 years and above used the internet for social media, reaching 2,468,167 people compared to other regencies/cities in Banten Province. The high number of social media users in Tangerang Regency should have the potential to increase the number of users of the BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services if social media marketing is effective in increasing brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency among social media users.

Source: 2023 National Socio-Economic Survey (Susenas), BPS (processed data)

Figure 2. Number of Population Aged 5 Years and Over Using the Internet for Social Media by Regency/City in Banten Province in 2023 (People)

Instagram has now become one of the most popular social media platforms in Indonesia. According to a report by We Are Social, as of January 2023, Indonesia had approximately 89.15 million active Instagram users. This makes Indonesia the fourth-largest user base in the world, after India (229.55 million), the United States (143.35 million), and Brazil (113.50 million).

Source: We Are Social report as of January 2023 in databoks.katadata.co.id.

Figure 3. Ten Countries with the Most Active Instagram Users as of January 2023 (Million Users)

In addition to its large number of users, Instagram has a high engagement rate due to its interactive features, such as Story, Reel, Like, Comment, and Share, which make it easy for users to interact directly with content and its creators (Sheldon & Bryant, 2016). This is the reason why BPS Tangerang Regency uses the Instagram platform as the main social media marketing channel to disseminate information on various statistical services at the PST BPS Tangerang Regency with the account name @bpskabtangerang. Similar to the number of direct visitors to the PST or users of offline statistical services, the 2023 BPS Tangerang Regency Social Media Utilization Report provides information that the number of Instagram posts on the @bpskabtangerang account is still low, namely 34 posts in 2023 or around 2 to 3 posts per month. This indicates that social media marketing through Instagram has not been carried out optimally in disseminating information on various statistical services at the PST BPS Tangerang Regency in 2023, so that brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency from the public, especially Instagram users, is still low. Furthermore, this will have an impact on the low number of users of statistical services at the PST BPS Tangerang Regency.

Based on the explanation above, it is deemed necessary to analyze the effectiveness of social media marketing through Instagram on brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency so that the right Instagram management strategy is obtained to increase brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency from Instagram users. Then, this will have a positive impact on increasing the number of users of PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services. This study has 3 (three) objectives. First, to analyze the use of BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account in disseminating information on PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services in 2023-2024. Second, to analyze the level of effectiveness of BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account utilization in increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency in 2023-2024. Third, to analyze the right Instagram management strategy to increase brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency so that it can increase the number of users of PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on the effectiveness of social media marketing through Instagram on brand awareness of the BPS-Statistics Indonesia's Integrated Statistics Service using qualitative methods has never been conducted at the central, provincial, or district/city levels, including Tangerang Regency. Putri et al.'s (2023) study discusses the influence of social media marketing through Instagram on the brand equity of the Statistics Indonesia (BPS). In other words, Putri et al.'s (2023) study does not specifically discuss the statistical service (BPS's Integrated Statistics Service) but rather the institution itself (BPS). Putri et al.'s (2023) study used quantitative methods, not qualitative methods, as used in this study. In Putri et al.'s (2023) study, brand awareness is one dimension of brand equity. However, Putri et al.'s (2023) study is still relevant as a reference for this study. Research by Putri et al. (2023) shows that Instagram plays a significant role in increasing brand awareness of the Statistics Indonesia (BPS), a government institution providing trusted statistical data. Through engaging and informative visual content such as photos, videos, and infographics, Instagram is able to reach a wide audience, particularly the younger generation, thereby strengthening public

awareness of the BPS brand. Instagram has become an effective strategic communication tool in building brand awareness and enhancing the reputation of government institutions, particularly BPS, in today's digital era. Furthermore, several previous studies are still relevant to this study, although they used different types of services: regional library services (perpusda) at the Library and Archives Service (Diperpusip). The PST BPS service is actually not much different from the regional library service. Both services are located within the respective service. The types of services provided by the perpusda and PST are quite similar. For example, the library provides access to reading books, while the PST BPS provides access to statistical publications. Furthermore, both services expect an increase in visitor numbers.

Research by Septianti et al. (2023) shows that social media marketing through Instagram plays a crucial role in increasing awareness and utilization of library services by disseminating information quickly and engagingly to users. This is evidenced by the analysis, which shows a strong correlation between Instagram usage and library utilization. With informative and interactive content, the North Jakarta Library and Archives Sub-Department's Instagram account (@perpusjkt_utara) has successfully encouraged users to become more familiar with the library's collections, services, and activities, thereby increasing visits and utilization. Community-building, content-sharing, and connections through Instagram have had a strong positive impact on public interest and engagement in library use. This underscores the crucial role of social media in strengthening library brand awareness and effectively increasing user engagement.

Research by Tasya et al. (2023) shows that social media marketing through Instagram plays a crucial role in increasing library brand awareness at the South Sulawesi Provincial Library and Archives Office by effectively promoting library collections, services, and activities to the wider community. Social media is not only a communication tool but also a marketing strategy that encourages an increase in the number of users and support for libraries. Library promotion through Instagram features such as Feed, Reels, Instastory, Highlight, Guide, and live broadcasts can reach various levels of users and build closer and more responsive interactions with the audience. Thus, Instagram is an effective means of expanding the reach of information, increasing public participation in library activities, and strengthening library branding in the current digital era. Promotion should be carried out not only in digital form but also in print to increase public visibility and awareness of the library's existence and services.

Chabibah's (2021) research shows that the Semarang Regency Regional Library's use of the Instagram Reels feature as a promotional medium has proven effective in introducing the library to the wider public and attracting visitors. Video content of library activities shared through Reels builds a positive image of the library, provides education, and creates the impression that the library is an interesting and dynamic place. Thus, social media serves as a strategic communication tool to expand the reach and increase brand awareness of libraries in today's digital era. Promotion through social media also facilitates direct interaction between libraries and users, thereby strengthening user relationships and loyalty to the institution.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative method with a case study approach. A case study is an approach that emphasizes in-depth exploration of a "bounded system", either in one specific case or some cases in detail so that it requires in-depth data and information mining (Creswell, 2015). This research was conducted by digging in-depth data and information related to the comparison of the utilization level of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account (@bpskabtangerang) in disseminating information on various PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services in two periods, namely 2023 and 2024. The results of the comparative analysis of the utilization level of the Instagram account are linked to the comparison of the number of statistical service users so that information is obtained on the effectiveness level of utilization of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram platform in increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency in 2023-2024.

The data and information collection methods in this study used observation and interviews. Observations in this study were conducted using social media analytics through observing content performance and audience behavior on the PST BPS Tangerang Regency content on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account. The application of social media analytics in this study was carried out by utilizing the Professional Dashboard menu on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account. The data and information collection methods through observation and interviews in this study are interrelated. The interview method was applied to dig deeper into data and information from the results of the observations conducted. Interviews were conducted face-to-face with 3 (three) informants who were employees of BPS Tangerang Regency. One member of the BPS Tangerang Regency Public Relations Team who is responsible for handling statistical promotions at PST BPS Tangerang Regency became the first informant because he had direct and in-depth knowledge regarding the management and utilization of BPS

Tangerang Regency Instagram to disseminate information on BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services. The first informant was also able to provide information on the effectiveness of social media marketing through Instagram in increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency based on his experience interacting with audiences on Instagram. One statistical service officer who most frequently serves users of statistical services at PST BPS Tangerang Regency became the second informant because he was able to provide information on the effectiveness of social media marketing through Instagram in increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency based on his experience interacting with users of statistical services. The Head of the BPS Tangerang Regency Public Relations Team became the third informant because he was able to provide information on the right Instagram management strategy in increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency. The Head of the Public Relations Team has the right to determine the policy for disseminating information on PST Tangerang Regency statistical services through the official BPS Tangerang Regency social media accounts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Utilization of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram Account in Disseminating Information on PST Statistics Services for BPS Tangerang Regency in 2023-2024

Compared to 2023, the performance of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram social media (@bpskabtangerang) experienced an increase in 2024. This is indicated by the increase in the number of Instagram posts from 34 posts in 2023 to 178 posts in 2024. However, based on observations on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account, the number of posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content is still very minimal. Although the number of posts showed a significant increase, reaching 423.53% in 2024, the proportion of the number of posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content to the total number of posts showed a very small increase. In 2023, the proportion of the number of posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content only reached 11.76%. In other words, only 4 posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content were published on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account. In 2024, only 22 posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content (12.36%).

Source: Observation Results of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram Account

Figure 4. Number of Posts and Number of Posts of PST Content Posts of BPS Tangerang Regency on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram Account in 2023-2024

Through an interview, the first source (the person in charge of statistical promotion at BPS Tangerang Regency) explained that the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account had not been optimally managed and utilized in 2023 due to limited human resources. In 2023, the BPS Tangerang Regency Public Relations Team had not yet been formed. Public relations activities, including the management of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account, were still managed by the General Sub-Section, so they could not focus on managing BPS Tangerang Regency's social media, especially Instagram. Instagram post content also still prioritized the dissemination of information on ceremonial activities at BPS Tangerang Regency, such as officer training and field activities, so it did not focus on the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services. The first resource person also explained that the condition of BPS Tangerang Regency's social media management, especially Instagram, is very different from 2024. The BPS Tangerang Regency Public Relations Team has been formed so that it has a special team that handles public relations activities including managing the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account for statistical promotion. Posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content have begun to be published in large numbers on the BPS Tangerang

Regency Instagram account, although the proportion has not increased significantly compared to 2023. This is due to the many routine activities at BPS Tangerang Regency in 2024, resulting in an increasing number of posts with content about BPS Tangerang Regency's routine activities. Even though the post content is not related to PST BPS Tangerang Regency, all posts with any content are always accompanied by an invitation to visit the BPS Tangerang Regency website either in the caption or on a special page after the main content page. Based on observations on BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account, post designs, particularly flyers, in 2023 lacked a standard format, either in terms of shape or color, making them appear untidy. In contrast, in 2024, flyer designs began to become more standardized, with a consistent purple hue. The first source explained that in 2024, the Public Relations Team was searching for a post design that truly embodied the Tangerang Regency BPS's identity. While the design format is still subject to change, the color scheme has been standardized with shades of purple, as directed by the Head of Tangerang Regency BPS. Purple is the brand color of Tangerang Regency. This contrasts sharply with the situation in 2023, when no uniform post design was considered.

Observations on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account also revealed that posts with PST content from BPS Tangerang Regency in 2024 were more varied than in 2023. In 2023, posts with PST content from BPS Tangerang Regency only provided an understanding to the audience that PST was a place to find data, giving the impression that PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical products were only data. In contrast, in 2024, additional information was provided to the audience regarding various statistical products, not only statistical data tables but also digital publications that can be downloaded through the BPS Tangerang Regency website. Explanatory content for some of the statistical data produced is available in both flyers and videos, making it more engaging. In addition, brief explanations of various BPS Tangerang Regency's statistical services, such as statistical consultations and statistical recommendations, have been used as one of the PST content materials for BPS Tangerang Regency on BPS Tangerang Regency's Instagram account. In fact, the physical condition of the complete and comfortable integrated statistical service room, which includes a reading room, kid zone, and consultation room, as well as straightforward service procedures, has been displayed on BPS Tangerang Regency's Instagram account. The first source acknowledged that the 2024 statistical promotion plan is indeed more focused. Posting of PST content by BPS Tangerang Regency has been scheduled at least once a month. Posts featuring statistical publication book releases have been consistently published year after year. Starting in 2024, all statistical publication book releases will be disseminated through the Tangerang Regency BPS Instagram account, with download links included in each post. Unlike in 2023, not all statistical publication book releases will be disseminated through the Tangerang Regency BPS Instagram account.

B. The Effectiveness of Utilizing the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram Account in Increasing Brand Awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency in 2023-2024

Along with the increase in the number of BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram posts, including posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content, the number of direct visitors to PST (users of offline statistical services) has increased. Based on the BPS Tangerang Regency Performance Report (Lakin), the number of direct visitors to PST (users of offline statistical services) increased by 233.33% from 12 visitors in 2023 to 40 visitors in 2024. In contrast, the number of external visitors who access statistical data and information through the BPS Tangerang Regency website (online service users) actually decreased by 17.62% from 39,787 visitors in 2023 to 32,778 visitors in 2024. Although the number of online service users showed a decline, it was still above the target of 17,000 visitors.

Source: BPS Tangerang Regency Performance Report (Lakin) 2023-2024

Figure 5. Number of Online Service Users (Thousand Visitors) and Number of Offline Service Users of PST BPS Tangerang Regency 2023-2024

The decline in the number of online service users, indicated by the number of external visitors accessing statistical services through the BPS Tangerang Regency website, does not mean that social media marketing through the dissemination of information on the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account is ineffective in increasing brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency from the public, especially Instagram users. Based on observations of Instagram accounts, especially the professional dashboard menu, several posts with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content increased the number of followers. During 2023 to 2024, 1 post with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content added a maximum of 16 followers. This occurred in 2024. In addition, each post with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content always invited audience interaction. One post in 2024 was able to invite 247 audience interactions (likes, comments, and shares). This was the most interaction during 2023-2024. The most viewed post with PST BPS Tangerang Regency content occurred in 2024, reaching 4,680 views.

The first source (the person in charge of statistical promotion for BPS Tangerang Regency) explained that the decline in the number of users of statistical services, both online and offline, does not necessarily indicate that social media marketing via Instagram is ineffective in increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency. According to the first source, every post with PST content always provides information on PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services and the statistical products produced so that viewers are at least aware of the various PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services. However, it cannot be denied that if the audience already knows information about PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services through Instagram posts, it does not necessarily immediately have a desire to access these statistical services. In other words, after knowing, it does not necessarily immediately have the urge to act. The first source emphasized that the number of users of online statistical services in 2023 was higher than in 2024 due to the recruitment of BPS partners for a major activity at BPS, particularly at BPS Tangerang Regency, in 2023. This activity was the 2023 Agricultural Census, which required many BPS partners to serve as field officers. The online written selection test with questions about BPS and BPS statistical data encouraged prospective officers to access BPS online statistical services, especially data access and statistical data publication on the BPS Tangerang Regency website.

The first speaker also explained some evidence that social media marketing through the dissemination of statistical service information from the BPS Tangerang Regency can increase brand awareness of BPS Tangerang Regency among the public, especially Instagram users. Many Instagram users sent direct messages (DM) to the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account admin after the statistical publication was broadcast. The audience asked how to access the statistical publication. Certain segments, such as local governments and academics, are always waiting for information on the release of the statistical publication and even ask when it will be released because they know that the necessary data is available in detail in the statistical publication. The Tangerang Regency Government always awaits information on the release of the statistical publication for planning, monitoring, and policy evaluation purposes. Academics, such as students, await information on the release of the statistical publication for the purposes of preparing college assignments and even final assignments.

The first source also acknowledged that some important information related to PST BPS Tangerang Regency (Public Statistics Service) had not been disseminated through the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account, such as the Zero Rupiah service. This service has the potential to increase the number of users of BPS Tangerang Regency's statistical services. Furthermore, information on how to access paid statistical services had not been disseminated on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account. These two factors contribute to the still minimal utilization of paid statistical services. The publication of the Analysis of the Data Needs Survey (SKD) Results from the BPS Tangerang Regency reports that only 1% of SKD respondents used paid services during 2024, specifically the purchase of microdata by a regional government agency within the Tangerang Regency Government. In 2023, not a single respondent used paid services. From 2023 to 2024, the most frequently used statistical service was Access to Statistical Products on the BPS Website. This is understandable, as observations on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account indicate that this type of service is the most frequently reported.

Table 1. Percentage of Statistics Service Users by Type of Statistics Service at the PST BPS Tangerang Regency 2023-2024

Types of Statistics Services	Percentage of Service Users	
	2023	2024
(1)	(2)	(3)
Access Statistical Products on the BPS Website	42%	45%
Library	5%	44%
Statistical Consultation	27%	5%
Statistics Recommendations	26%	5%
Purchase of Micro Data/ Statistical Work Area Maps	0%	1%

Source: Analysis of the Results of the Data Needs Survey (SKD) of BPS Tangerang Regency 2023-2024, BPS Tangerang Regency

The second source (the statistics service officer who most frequently serves users of statistics services) also agreed with the first source that social media, especially Instagram, is suitable for use as a strategic communication tool to expand reach and increase brand awareness. Many direct visitors to the PST BPS Tangerang Regency (offline service visitors) stated that information on statistical services PST BPS Tangerang Regency was obtained from the Instagram of BPS Tangerang Regency. In fact, some visitors have the desire to visit the PST BPS Tangerang Regency directly because Instagram shows the physical condition of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency comfortable where reading rooms, consultation rooms, and kid zones are provided. Users of this offline service are not only from Tangerang Regency but also from outside Tangerang Regency. Some users of statistics services prefer to visit the PST BPS Tangerang Regency directly because they are still confused about using the online services PST BPS Tangerang Regency. Information on the Instagram of BPS Tangerang Regency only shows the existence of statistical services but does not provide information on procedures for accessing online statistical services. If users of statistics services directly visit the PST BPS Tangerang Regency, they will be immediately directed by the statistics service officer, thus resolving user confusion in accessing various statistical services PST BPS Tangerang Regency.

The second source also emphasized that the decline in the number of online service users in 2024 was due to users using the services inappropriately. For example, statistics service users directly requested macro data from statistics service officers via WhatsApp personal chat, even though the data could be accessed on BPS Tangerang Regency website, thus reducing the number of online service users. Similarly, for statistical consultations, users did not use the statistical consultation menu on the BPS Tangerang Regency website but instead used WhatsApp personal chat with statistics service officers. Furthermore, the second source reported that users of the statistical recommendation service are still limited to regional government agencies (sectoral statistics). Information that this service is free for non-governmental agencies conducting statistical activities has not been disseminated through BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account. This also reduces the potential for increasing the number of users of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical service. Based on the explanation above, the use of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account as a social media marketing channel actually plays a role in increasing brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency with various statistical services provided. This is similar to research conducted by Putri et al. (2023) which shows that the use of Instagram plays a significant role in increasing brand awareness of BPS as a government institution that provides trusted statistical data. This statement is also supported by research by Septianti et al. (2023), Tasya et al. (2023), and Chabibah (2021) which states that promotional media has proven

effective in introducing services to the wider community and attracting interest in visits. In the case of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency, in general, the dissemination of information on the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services can increase public awareness of the existence of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services, thus increasing the use of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services if promoted clearly and attractively on the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account through various features provided by Instagram. In general, social media marketing through Instagram is an effective medium for increasing brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency. This is evidenced by the increase in the number of direct visitors to the PST BPS Tangerang Regency (offline users), the increase in the number of followers for each additional post containing PST BPS Tangerang Regency content, and the interaction between each post and the content. The interaction between each Instagram post containing BPS Tangerang Regency content indicates a strong audience drive to pay attention to the post. This impacts brand awareness, at least to the Brand Recognition stage.

The level of brand awareness for each segment of statistical service users certainly varies. For the general public, on average, the dissemination of information on the PST statistical service of BPS Tangerang Regency through the Tangerang Regency BPS Instagram account can increase brand awareness to the level of Brand Recall. For example, when a service user needs macro data covering the Tangerang Regency area, the user immediately remembers the Tangerang Regency BPS website as a reference for macro data. However, for the local government segment, the dissemination of information on the PST statistical service of the BPS Tangerang Regency through the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account can increase brand awareness to the level of Brand Dominance. For example, if a regional apparatus within the Tangerang Regency Government wishes to conduct a statistical activity, the regional apparatus will use the statistical recommendation service at the PST BPS Tangerang Regency. This is also supported by regulations related to the implementation of One Data at the Tangerang Regency Level (Tangerang Regent Regulation Number 88 of 2021) and the Tangerang Regent's Circular which explains that every statistical activity carried out by regional apparatus within the Tangerang Regency Government must obtain a statistical recommendation from the Tangerang Regency BPS.

Research conducted by Septianti et al. (2023), Tasya et al. (2023), and Chabibah (2021), which used library services as the object of research, stated that the promotion of library services through Instagram significantly influenced the increase in the number of library service users. This is slightly different from the PST service of BPS Tangerang Regency. The PST statistical service of BPS Tangerang Regency is not yet familiar with library services, especially since library services can be enjoyed by all ages. For certain services, especially online statistics services, special promotional methods are needed to attract the interest of service users. For example, by adding video content on how to access online statistics services that are complete and interesting. This online service information that is too brief can increase brand awareness but does not continue to lead to potential users' actions to use the online service because the existing information does not provide clarity for potential online service users. The use of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account as a social media marketing channel actually plays a role in increasing brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency, but the use of the Instagram account is considered not optimal by BPS Tangerang Regency in promoting the PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services. so that it does not immediately increase the number of statistical service users. This is evidenced by the increase in the number of content but not accompanied by an increase in the variety of PST BPS Tangerang Regency content. The increase in the number of PST BPS Tangerang Regency content only refers to one type of service, namely free macro data access and statistical publications through the BPS Tangerang Regency website. Zero rupiah services, online statistical consultation services, paid services, and statistical recommendation services have not been intensively promoted.

The Right Instagram Management Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency. The decline in the number of users of online statistics services in 2024 does not necessarily indicate the inefficiency of Instagram as a digital marketing channel in increasing brand awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency. The increase in brand awareness remains, but has not been accompanied by significant action to utilize the statistics services available at the PST. This is due to the suboptimal use of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account to disseminate information about the PST. Based on the explanation in the previous section, it was found that there is still a lot of important information related to potential services that can increase the number of service users that have not been highlighted in the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account, such as zero rupiah services, online statistical consultation services, paid services, and statistical recommendation services that have not been intensively promoted. The right Instagram management strategy to increase Brand Awareness of PST BPS Tangerang Regency can be directed at adding Instagram posts with complete explanatory content and procedures for accessing the four services. In addition, adding complete explanatory content and procedures for accessing online statistical services is also necessary to increase the number of online statistical service users. Referring to research conducted by Tasya et

al. (2023), other methods or channels are needed to increase user loyalty in statistical services to avoid a decline in the number of users of the PST statistical services of BPS Tangerang Regency. In contrast to the method recommended by Tasya et al. (2023) by adding non-digital promotional media, BPS Tangerang Regency can implement email marketing. BPS Tangerang Regency actually has an email address that can be used for email marketing, namely bps3603@bps.go.id. This email is listed on BPS Tangerang Regency website and every BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram content. Until now, this email has only been used to respond to requests for statistical services and products submitted by users via email. BPS Tangerang Regency needs to optimize this email for email marketing. This begins with conducting a Data Needs Survey (SKD) using Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI). The Electronic Data Needs Survey (SKD) questionnaire is sent to the user's email address that has been recorded when receiving statistical services and products. For your information, all users will be asked for their email address when accessing statistical services and products, both online and offline. The results of the Data Needs Survey (SKD) will reveal the services, products, and statistical data generally required by statistical service users. To increase user loyalty, the PST BPS Tangerang Regency Team can send the latest information on the services, products, and statistical data needed to the email addresses of those users.

The third resource person (Head of the Public Relations Team of BPS Tangerang Regency) explained that the public relations team has already prepared a plan to add content to PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical service. The number of Instagram posts as of April 30, 2025, reached 150. The Public Relations Team has prepared a grand design for Instagram content. Each post will remain purple to blend with the Tangerang Regency Government, which has designated purple as the brand color of Tangerang Regency. This is considering that the potential user segment of PST BPS Tangerang Regency is the Tangerang Regency Government. For any post, two special pages will be provided after the main content page. These two special pages contain a reminder page for the types of PST BPS Tangerang Regency statistical services and a page inviting visitors to visit BPS Tangerang Regency website. BPS Tangerang Regency will also optimize the use of the reels feature on Instagram. This is due to the high audience interest in viewing information presented through the reels feature on Instagram. Optimizing the use of the Instagram Reels feature to increase service users and increase user loyalty is similar to research by Chabibah (2021). According to Chabibah (2021), the Instagram Reels feature is a proven promotional tool for introducing services to the wider public and attracting visitors.

CONCLUSION

The BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account saw an increase in the number of posts from 2023 to 2024, but content focused on the PST statistical service remained minimal. The formation of the BPS Tangerang Regency Public Relations Team in 2024 improved the management of the BPS Tangerang Regency Instagram account, with a more varied and informative design and content. Increased interaction on Instagram contributed to an increase in offline service visitors, which indicates increased brand awareness of the PST BPS Tangerang Regency. Although the number of online statistics service users has decreased, this does not reduce Instagram's effectiveness as a promotional medium. Instagram is at least effective in increasing brand awareness to the level of brand recognition and brand recall. For the local government segment, Instagram can increase brand awareness to the point of Brand Dominance. However, information about paid services and procedures for accessing online services is still lacking, resulting in suboptimal use of these services. The promotional strategy is not optimal because it has not yet covered all essential services, including zero rupiah services.

Suggestion

BPS Tangerang Regency is advised to improve its Instagram content by providing more comprehensive information about zero-rupiah services, statistical consultations, paid services, and procedures for accessing all statistical services to better understand and encourage audiences to use these services. BPS Tangerang Regency also needs to increase the variety of content, such as video tutorials and reels, to attract users' attention and facilitate understanding of online services. Optimizing the use of email marketing as an active communication channel is also important to maintain and increase user loyalty. Education regarding procedures for using statistical services must be strengthened so that users can access services appropriately and efficiently. Consistency in the use of design and the color purple must be maintained to strengthen the BPS Tangerang Regency brand identity. Finally, regular evaluation and monitoring of content and interactions is essential so that marketing strategies can be tailored to user needs and preferences.

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